

**TEACHERS' TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT
KNOWLEDGE (TPACK) AND STUDENTS' SELF – EFFICACY:
PREDICTORS ON MATHEMATICS
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between teachers' TPACK, students' self-efficacy, and mathematics academic performance. The researcher employed descriptive-correlational-causal research designs in this study and used proportionate stratified random sampling to select two hundred seventy-seven (277) junior high school students from Cabanglasan National High School in Bukidnon as participants. Information was collected from participants using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. Students have a high level of self-efficacy, whereas teachers have a moderate level of TPACK, as indicated by the mean and standard deviation results. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) analysis revealed that the seven TPACK components and students' self-efficacy in terms of perceived control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning have a substantial positive correlation with students' academic performance in mathematics. The best predictor of all eleven variables is students' self-regulated learning. Other predictors are perceived control, pedagogical knowledge, persistence, pedagogical content knowledge, and teachers' content knowledge. These data imply that the TPACK of teachers and the self-efficacy of students influence mathematics performance.

Keywords: TPACK, Self - Efficacy, Technology - integration, 21st Century Educators, Mathematics Education

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is indeed a fundamental subject that plays a crucial role in preparing students for the knowledge-based economy and the fast-paced world of the 21st century. Nonetheless, the Philippines, among many other nations, performed poorly on international tests in mathematics and science administered to students in grades four and eight as reported in the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) in 2019 (Mullis et al., 2020). They also noted that only 1% of Filipino students met the high standard for those who can apply conceptual comprehension to solve problems. In the 2018, Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), Filipino students ranked last, out of 79 nations, in reading comprehension and second-lowest in mathematical and scientific literacy (OECD, 2019). Furthermore, in the Southeast Asia

Primary Learning Metrics (SAP-PLM) in 2019, the Philippines was also in the bottom half of the six countries in reading, mathematics, and writing literacy (UNICEF and SEAMEO, 2020). The National Achievement Test for three consecutive years (2012–2015) measuring 21st Century Skills among Grade 10 students of the Department of Education, Bukidnon division, set a record for an average mean percentage score of 44.34 percent and showed that mathematics was the second lowest of the five core subjects.

This study explored and investigated several factors that may have a predicted impact or limitation on the student's academic performance, including the disadvantages of the sudden shift in educational platforms brought on by the pandemic. The educators' knowledge of technology, pedagogy, and subject matter based on the TPACK framework and their students' confidence or sense of self-efficacy plays a part in this. TPACK stands for a complete package of knowledge of technology, pedagogy, and content that a teacher must have to attain an effective infusion of technology in education. This study explicitly tested the seven different TPACK domains, including technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and content knowledge (CK), as well as technological pedagogical knowledge (TPK), technological content knowledge (TCK), and technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK). This study explored the students' self-efficacy alongside the teachers' TPACK. It specifically explored the four constructs of self-efficacy of the students, such as perceived control, competence, persistence, and self-regulated learning.

Technology integration through the TPACK framework is significant during crucial times of unprecedented health crises and in the new typical education setup when in-person learning is impossible. This model places as basis on teachers' familiarity with relevant technologies, pedagogical strategies, and subject content. Educators can also utilize the TPACK framework in remediation, enrichment, and in creating instructional materials. Besides, the realization of this study lays out a deep understanding of the teachers' educational practices and awareness of students' intrinsic coping standards toward achieving academic goals. Thus, variables affect math instruction, remediation, and intervention programs to match students' demands.

FRAMEWORK

Student performance is a by-product of multiple factors affecting it. One is the students' self-efficacy (Ahmad & Safaria, 2013). Underlying this factor is the self-efficacy theory (SET), a subset of Bandura's (1986) social cognitive theory. High-self-efficacy persons are those who understand what they are capable of and can come up with a plan and an output, while persons with low self-efficacy cannot perform tasks given to them (Bandura, 1982). Self-efficacy has emerged as an effective predictor of students' better academic performance (Tossavainen et al., 2021).

The self-determination theory developed by Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan in the mid-1980s provides a foundation for studying students' self-efficacy as a factor of academic achievement (Deci & Ryan, 2000). This theory states that people can become self-determined and motivated when their competence, connection, and autonomy are satisfied. This study supported the sub-variables, such as perceived control and competence, as being assumed to be the predictors of academic performance.

The Eccles & Wigfield (2002) Theory of Expectancy and Value relates academic success and persistence to students' expectations and the task's relevance. This theory also suggests that an individual will tend to position himself around deciding which task is valuable to engage in, which corresponds to his high expectations. A student with high persistence commits to continuing to perform a task and striving for success because the task is crucial to him (Roland et al., 2016). Self-regulated theory was first proposed by Zimmerman (2000), who argued that a successful learner could direct his or her attention, focus, and effort toward academic tasks (Zimmerman, 2015). A self-regulated student evaluates his or her work and output in the pursuit of a goal. According to empirical evidence, self-regulated learning is a variable linked to educational outcomes.

Furthermore, technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) is a robust framework which is the acronym for "total package of teachers' knowledge," to express this confluence of content, pedagogy, and technology integration in the classroom (Thompson & Mishra, 2008, p. 38). According to Mishra and Koehler (2006), TPACK is "the integration of educators' knowledge of technology, pedagogy, and content." This definition adds technological considerations to Shulman's (1986) original notion of knowledge of appropriately combining the instructional pedagogy and content, also known as pedagogical content knowledge (PCK). Knowledge of technology (TK), pedagogy (PK), content (CK), technology and pedagogy (TPK), pedagogy and content (PCK), technology and content (TCK), and technology, pedagogy, and mastery of the subject content (TPACK) are the components that makeup TPACK (Koehler, n.d., & Schilis, 2018). These seven (7) domains of TPACK, as used as constructs in this study, are believed to be indispensable in providing quality teaching and education in general.

The theories underpinning this study's variables, teachers' technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) and students' self-efficacy, aim to improve students' academic performance. In his Theory of Educational Productivity, Walberg (1981) proposes three consistent proximal determinants of learners' academic achievement: aptitude, instructional time and quality, and the learning environment. The fundamental premise of the theory is to identify the factors that influenced students' academic performance and how they did so. Thus, a student's academic performance is unquestionably a research topic for educators (Sæle et al., 2017).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study's primary objective was to identify the variable that best predicts Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics. Specifically, the study aimed to: (1) to determine the level of technological pedagogical content knowledge of the teachers as perceived by the students in terms of Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Content Knowledge (CK), Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Technological Content Knowledge (TCK), and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK); (2) to determine the level of Students' Self – Efficacy in terms of Perceived Control, Competence, Persistence, and Self-regulated Learning; (3) to determine the level of students' Academic Performance in Mathematics (4) to correlate students' academic performance in mathematics and technological pedagogical content knowledge of the teachers, and students' self-

efficacy; (5) to establish what variables best predict students' academic performance in Mathematics.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used Descriptive Correlational and Causal Design to determine the relationship between teachers' technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK), Student" self-efficacy, and the predictors that influence students' academic performance in mathematics. This study employed a correlational approach to identify the relationships between the four variables of students' self-efficacy regarding their academic performance and the seven TPACK domains. According to Creswell (2009), the correlational research design is appropriate when a researcher ought to describe and measure the degree of relationship between two or more variables or sets of scores and when One wishes to see if there is a relationship between variables or to predict an outcome. Descriptive Research is used when it involves collecting information through data review, surveys, interviews, or observation (Gay, 1987). This type of Research best describes the level of quantifiable characteristics of the subject.

On the other hand, causal Research best fits studies that attempt a cause-effect relationship between two or more variables (Kravitz, n.d). The study utilized a combination of the three types of Research, namely, Descriptive Correlational and Causal Design. This study explored identifying the level of students' perception of their teachers' TPACK and their perception of their level of self-efficacy. Moreover, this study analyzed the significant relationship between independent and dependent variables and, finally, investigated the effect of independent variables such as students' perceived teachers' technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) and self-efficacy towards the dependent variable, the academic performance concerning math.

Research Setting

The study was conducted at Cabanglasan National High School, where the researcher works as a full-time teacher. It is located at Purok – 5, Poblacion, Cabanglasan, Bukidnon. The school comprises 40 teaching and non-teaching personnel from Junior High School and 24 teaching and non-teaching personnel from Senior High School.

The researcher intended to implement the study in this school because learning gaps among learners are notable, especially regarding their mathematics performance. Technology infrastructure of the said school is somehow functional although stability of internet connectivity is one of the undebatable point of concerns at present. Students have at least cellphones, and the majority of classrooms in the study's locale have smart televisions that can be used as supplementary technological teaching and learning tools. In addition, teachers were trained in synchronous and asynchronous learning delivery techniques as part of DepEd's initiative to equip teachers with the necessary skills during the restriction on in-person classes due to the pandemic. It is also richly populated with diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds, thus, creating a good mark of representing various characters and giving an equal chance to be the data source for the study.

Equally important are the Department of Education-mandated mathematics-related activities in which the school actively participates each year.

Participants of the Study and Sampling Procedure

Based on the partial enrolment report as of August 2022 generated from the Learners Information System, the total population of Junior High School students is 912. Specifically, it comprises 247 students from the grade 7 curriculum, 242 students from the grade 8 curriculum, 205 students from the grade 9 curriculum, and 218 students from the grade 10 curriculum. The sampling process of this study involved two stages, identifying the strata sample size and randomly selecting the participants from each identified population in strata. The researcher sent a consent letter to the participants' parents, whose ages ranged from 12 to 17 years old. Actual study participants were those who provided their consent. In contrast, those who refused were excluded as participants.

In computing the suitable sample size, this study used SLOVIN's Formula. Slovin's Formula allows the researcher to take the sample from the target population, ensuring a reasonable degree of accuracy results (Ellen, 2017). On the level of accuracy, this study adopted the confidence level of 95%, which means there is a 95% probability that the confidence interval will contain the true population mean (Sullivan, n.d). The computation of sample size using Slovin's Formula; $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$, where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the degree of error at 5% is; Sample Size; $n = \frac{912}{1 + 912(0.05)^2} = 277$.

However, the researcher employed Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling in selecting the participants. As obtained, there were 75 grade 7 participants, 74 grade 8 participants, 62 grade 9 participants and 66 grade 10 participants. A total of 277 samples.

Research Instruments

With the author's permission, the researcher used a survey instrument called the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale for Filipino Junior High School Students (ASES - FJHS) of Dullas (2018) to measure students' perceptions of their self-efficacy in learning mathematics. The teacher-researcher intentionally chose this instrument due to its locality criterion. However, with the author's permission, the researcher used a modified survey questionnaire based on the TPACK instrument Bingimlas (2018) used to gauge students' perceptions of their teachers' TPACK in the classroom.

Part I of the Questionnaire is about the participant's demographic information, specifically the participant's name (optional), ethnic tribe, gender, and age. Part II is the perception questionnaires on the teacher's level of TPACK, and Part III is the students' self-efficacy. All sub-variables in this study utilized the 5 – point Likert scale with assigned numerical values ranging from strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), Agree (4), and strongly agree (5). Part II comprises seven (7) sub-variables having forty – three (43) items all in all. It contains seven (7) items that assessed teachers' content knowledge and seven (7) items measuring their understanding

of pedagogy. Six (6) questions set teachers' technological pedagogical knowledge, and seven (7) probed their pedagogical content knowledge. Additionally, five (5) items evaluated teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge. Thirty-three items comprise Part III of the survey questionnaire, which focused on students' perceptions of their self-efficacy in mathematical learning. Eight (8) items assessed students' perceived control, nine (9) measured competence, eight (8) assessed persistence, and eight (8) assessed self-regulated learning. For the students' performance, the researcher opted to access mathematics grades through the respective subject teachers in each grade level. The Department of Education Order No. 8, section 2015, serves as the basis for students' grade calculated values.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The content of the survey questionnaire was validated by three specialists in educational technology, mathematical education, and language for analysis, enhancement, and recommendation. A panel of relevant experts could establish the validity of the questionnaire by exploring theoretical constructs (Bolarinwa, 2016). On the other hand, the researcher conducted pilot testing with 30 students not included in the sample to carry out a reliability test of the questionnaire. This study utilized Cronbach's alpha coefficient for its internal consistency reliability test, taken from the participant's responses. Bolarinwa (2016) further noted that the reliability coefficient (alpha) could range from 0 to 1, with 0 representing a questionnaire that is not reliable and 1 representing a highly reliable questionnaire.

Generally, the reliability test result of the instruments has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.93 and an interpretation of being acceptable and reliable. In SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences, by IBM incorporated), a reliability coefficient (alpha) of 0.70 or higher is considered acceptable. All questions in the instruments used in this study were all reliable and accepted based on the result.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher conducted the research in the second quarter of the school year 2022–2023, in November 2022. Before the implementation of the investigation, the researcher had submitted a permission letter to the Dean of the Liceo de Cagayan University, School of teacher education, seeking approval to conduct the study. Subsequently, the researcher submitted another permission letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Bukidnon, the public schools district supervisor of Cabanglasan, and the school principal of the locale of the study. After the approval was granted, the researcher secured clearance from the Research Ethics Board of the Liceo de Cagayan University, and data-gathering procedures followed. The survey questionnaire was first distributed to 30 respondents not included in the study's sample population for pilot testing. After this, relevant experts processed the reliability test and executed the content validation of the tool.

After receiving permission from the school principal, the investigator selected participants through room-to-room selection. An informed consent letter for students and their parents was distributed to those randomly selected participants of each grade level based on the number of samples per stratum, particularly those aged 12 to 17. Participation was voluntary. Participants

were limited to those who gave explicit permission to participate in the study. The researcher administered a room-to-room distribution of the survey questionnaire. Answering the 76-item survey questionnaire took the participants approximately 15 minutes to finish. To complete the survey questionnaire, participants had to read and input their responses. This study provided no direct advantages to the participants. However, they were informed that their responses could help the study become a reality.

The researcher treated the information gleaned from this study's participants with strict confidentiality and anonymity, and there was no chance of a privacy breach. The people who have access to the gathered data are no one else except the researcher, the research adviser, the statistician, and other people who engaged in data analysis. This study's findings will be disseminated to other students to be utilized in their future research. The completed paper of this research is available at the campus libraries of Liceo de Cagayan University. Before publishing, the researcher will consider the university and the participants' approval. They will also not be addressed or specified in the publication. Lastly, the researcher, declares that there is no personal conflict of interest that may arise from the application and submission of this research.

Statistical Treatment and Data Analysis

The researcher used statistical tools to analyze and interpret the results after the data was coded and tallied.

Descriptive statistics, such as the mean and standard deviation, were used to answer problems 1, 2, and 3 about students' perceptions of their mathematics teachers' technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge (TPACK), as well as their sense of self - efficacy and their grades in mathematics.

To know the significance of the relationship between the independent variables (teachers' TPACK and students' self-efficacy) and the student's academic performance as the dependent variable, Problem 4 used the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r).

Lastly, Problem 5 was analyzed and answered using multiple regression analysis to determine what variable best predicts the students' academic performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study found that mathematics educators have a moderate level of pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, and technological knowledge. The teachers also possessed moderate technological pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and technological content knowledge. Correspondingly, teachers also have a moderate level of technological pedagogical content knowledge. Students' self-efficacy was also measured. Results showed that students have high self-efficacy in terms of perceived control (3.56), moderately high self-efficacy in terms of competence (3.33), high self-efficacy in terms of persistence (3.74), and moderately high self-efficacy in terms of self-regulated learning (3.47). The mean average grade of participants is 83.22, which has an interpretation of satisfactory.

A correlation analysis revealed that all independent variables used in the study are significantly related to student's academic performance in mathematics. Such independent variables are technological knowledge ($P = .001$), pedagogical knowledge ($P = .001$), content knowledge ($P = .000$), technological pedagogical knowledge ($P = .000$), pedagogical content knowledge ($P = .000$), perceived control ($P = .000$), competence ($P = .02$), persistence ($P = .000$), and self-regulated learning ($P = .000$). This result suggests that the student's mathematics performance will improve if these eleven variables improve.

Among all eleven variables presented and analyzed in this study, six statistically significantly predicted the students' academic performance in mathematics. Based on the standardized beta coefficients, the strongest predictor is the students' self-efficacy in terms of self-regulated learning ($\beta = .197$), followed by students' perceived control ($\beta = .137$), teachers' pedagogical knowledge ($\beta = .134$), students' persistence ($\beta = .105$), teachers' pedagogical content knowledge ($\beta = .033$), and teachers' content knowledge ($\beta = .023$).

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are developed based on the findings:

Math educators have a moderate level of knowledge in terms of their TK, PK, CK, TPK, PCK, TCK, and TPCK. The level of students' self-efficacy in learning mathematics is high in terms of perceived control, moderately high in terms of competence, high in terms of persistence, and moderately high in terms of self-regulated learning.

With the blended learning approach of the Department of Education in the first quarter of the school year 2022–2023, the mean score shows that the students have satisfactory academic performance in mathematics.

A statistically significant relationship exists between the student's academic performance in mathematics and the seven domains of teachers' technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK). The seven TPACK domains are pedagogical knowledge, content knowledge, technological knowledge, technological content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, technological pedagogical knowledge, and technological pedagogical content knowledge. Moreover, a statistically significant relationship also exists between students' self-efficacy and the academic performance of students in mathematics. The four constructs of students' self-efficacy are perceived control, persistence, competence, and self-regulated learning. This finding, therefore, corroborates the rejection of Null Hypothesis 1 (H_01).

Self-regulated learning is the best predictor of all eleven sub-variables. Following it is perceived control, pedagogical knowledge, persistence, pedagogical content knowledge, and content knowledge. This notion means that these six variables statistically significantly predicted the students' academic performance in mathematics. Therefore, with the results shown in this study, Hypothesis 2 (H_02) is rejected. The finding means that if these six (6) variables increase while all other latent variables remain constant, the student's academic performance in math is likely to increase as well.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are therefore endorsed:

Despite the DepEd's initiative to make internet connectivity available, a consistent and higher budget for steady and fast connectivity and accessibility may be provided to all schools to ensure optimum usage of interactive technology learning tools among mathematics teachers. The Department of Education may strengthen its sustainable partnership with other agencies and NGOs for collective ownership of the solution to the problem of a lack of technology infrastructure among public schools in the Philippines. The high cost of technological tools might be the biggest hindrance to attaining ICT-based education. It is therefore highly suggested to establish a continual partnership with potential donors domestically and internationally in order to meet the department's needs.

In constructing or redesigning the mathematics curriculum instruction, curriculum policymakers may consider the significant variables and predictors identified by the study's findings to refocus the objectives for planning, content, method, implementation, and evaluation.

Supervisors and Education Program Specialists may provide quality technical assistance to mathematics teachers in recalibrating their knowledge in mathematics, technology integration, and teaching pedagogy. A further recommendation is a quarterly or yearly professional development and training program for teachers about updates on technology in teaching so that Philippine teachers will be at par with other countries' teachers regarding technology integration in education based on the TPACK framework. They may also provide educators with a complete educational technology package. These may include software and applications that could direct teachers' work in an easy, friendly, and time-efficient way of teaching. As information is rapidly updated, teachers, too, must not be left behind. They, too, must keep up with educational trends around the world.

The researcher suggests that there will be close monitoring and evaluation of teachers' progress. The school principals are the best authorities for direct monitoring. They may consider the strengths and weaknesses of teachers' teaching so that there will be a provision of appropriate training. Sharing of updates and best practices among educators may be adopted through the district- or school-level in-service training. Decisions on action implementations made by school leaders should be based on empirical evidence or research findings to ensure that issues and concerns are properly addressed.

When it comes to developing or strengthening students' self-efficacy, educators, school guidance counselors, and even Gender and Development school focal persons can reinforce activities that allow students to reflect on their own experiences with overcoming challenges. A symposium on time management, strategic planning, and coping with stress and failures can also boost students' self-efficacy. Teachers may include a reflection and discussion on students' error analysis and confusion in their classroom activities and consistent guidance. Moreover, strengthening early literacy and numeracy skills in students is highly recommended for primary educators.

Future researchers could incorporate mediating variables, especially in integrating technology in the classroom. They may have a more comprehensive study of this through

triangulation of the findings, such as through interviews with teachers and students, and utilizing a more extensive scope and sample. They may also explore structural equation modeling and path analysis of future research similar to this study.

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